

AN ANALYTICAL MODEL TO PREDICT THE STIFFNESS OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL WOVEN ANGLE INTERLOCK COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The University of Ulster specialises in the research and development of 3D woven carbon fibre composites. Specific 3D weave architectures that are dominated by long continuous lengths of reinforcing tows in the orthogonal 0/90° directions for maximum inplane strength, and have a small amount of binder tow content (>5%) in-order to suppress delaminations were manufactured. An analytical modelling approach for the prediction of geometric characteristics and stiffness properties of 3D woven angle interlock composite laminates has been formulated. The model is driven from readily available weaver specified data and mechanical property data from the constituent material manufacturers datasheet. The model predicts geometric characteristics such as the proportions of fibre volume fraction in each orthogonal direction, overall fibre volume fraction, areal density and thickness of the fabric preform. The parameters calculated by the geometric part of the model form the inputs for the stiffness calculation in each of the orthogonal directions of the composite unit cell.

Keywords: 3-Dimensional reinforcement; Carbon fibre; Fabrics/textiles; Analytical modelling;

1 Introduction

The use of advanced two dimensional (2D) laminar type composites are the traditional choice of materials in the aerospace industry[1]. From a performance perspective, these materials offer high specific strength and stiffness in the direction that the fibrous reinforcement flows. Generally, layers or plies of either dry or prepreg reinforcement material will be cut, aligned and stacked to create the preform which has the approximate geometry and dimensions of the finished component. Constructing the preform in this way is lengthy and laborious whilst additional costs are incurred from the special storage requirements for prepreg materials. Also the 2D laminate will have poor impact and through-the-thickness mechanical properties due to the absence of fibrous reinforcement in these directions unless the preform

undergoes an additional process to stitch the layers together[2-3]. Therefore, to address these performance and manufacturing type problems consideration is been given to manufacturing methods such as three dimensional (3D) weaving. The 3D weaving process allows for the tailored placement of reinforcing tows in the X, Y, and Z axis directions. Therefore, the 3D weave architecture can be tailored toward the needs of a particular application. However, this creates a difficulty for an engineer designing the component in that they as well as designing the part must also consider the design of the actual weave architecture of the material as well.

At the University of Ulster a design system (figure 1) provides the designer with the facility to evaluate 3D weave architectures based on basic inputs such as the geometric arrangement and the constituent materials properties. The geometric arrangement details the weave architecture i.e. the relative positions of the reinforcement in the warp and weft directions. The constituent materials would include manufacturer's data on the fibrous reinforcement and matrix elements of the composite. This information is collected and becomes the composite unit cell, which is the smallest representative volumetric element that contains the information used to perform downstream predictions of the geometric and stiffness properties. Buchanan et al [5] described a model for the prediction of the geometric properties that predict the physical properties of the unit cell such as overall dimensions in the X, Y, and Z directions, areal density, overall fibre volume fraction as well as the proportions of reinforcement in each direction. The model also provided the required input data for the analytical model to predict the stiffness of the unit cell described here. The modelling strategy described here is aimed toward engineers and designers in industry that would not generally have an expert understanding of 3D woven composite design. It provides quick assessment of the geometric and basic mechanical properties of 3D woven composites aiding the selection of suitable weave architectures early on in the design process. The model receives the necessary input parameters from readily available sources and does not demand massive computer processing power.

There are various Finite Element (FE) and analytically based models available for the prediction of the mechanical properties of 3D composites. However, it is generally accepted that due to the complexity of the weave architecture and significant computer processing power required[6-7] with FE modelling of 3D woven composites, that analytical methods are more suited and useful for initial predictions of mechanical performance. For instance Tan et al[8] presented an FE and two analytical models to predict the elastic constants of 3D Through-The-Thickness (T-T-T) bound angle interlock composites. They concluded that both analytical models correlated well with the predicted results from the FE modelling strategy, and that the FE results were on par with those predicted using the analytical Orientation Averaging (OA)[9] model and Cox et al's FE model, better known as the 'binary model'[10]. However, the authors did not indicate which model would be the most useful for a given problem.

Cox et al[9] developed the 'orientation averaging' (OA) model and also the Modified OA model. The OA model assessed analytically the stiffness of the 3D composite where the tows within a small volume are orientated as unidirectional composites. The warp stuffers, weft fillers and warp binders are split into 'domains' each occupying a fraction of the total composite volume, where the overall macroscopic properties are calculated by averaging the response of a representative small volume applied to loads. In the Modified OA model a 'stiffness knockdown factor' (SKF) incorporates the effect of waviness in each of the tow directions, where it is stated by the author that waviness of the tows in the woven reinforcement results

in a reduction of elastic modulus. The SKF was aimed at reducing the calculated values for stiffness in order to increase accuracy compared to experimentally measured values. However, derivation of the SKF requires actual microscopic observations of the weave architecture in question, where in order to do this the composite must be manufactured first.

Wu et al[6] developed a modelling strategy whereby the modulus of a 3D woven orthogonal T-T-T bound composite unit cell was predicted. They segmented or ‘discretised’ the unit cell into layers and then each layer into elements where each element behaves like a unidirectional composite. The modulus of in each direction was obtained analytically and compared to Cox et al’s OA model and experimental results[9]. Comparison of these results clearly indicate that the modelling strategy developed by Wu had increased accuracy over the OA models, although still higher than the experimentally measured values, which can be explained because of the reliance on idealised geometric parameters.

The modelling approach described in this paper will focus on prediction of the tensile modulus of 3D woven angle interlock composites. The model develops the strategy adopted by Wu et al[6] who formulated a model to predict the stiffness of orthogonally bound 3D woven composite unit cells. The unit cell is treated as an assembly consisting of layers containing unidirectional elements (which are fibrous tows encased in resin). The new model was formulated accounting for the different type of weave architecture examined in this paper as well as new expressions to describe more accurately the contribution of the various groups of elements on each layer and volume fraction of each element within a layer compared to the previous approach. The predictions from the new model is compared to experimentally measured data and also with the new expressions exchanged for equivalent terms used in [6].

2 Stiffness model

On the macro-scale or unit cell level the composite is homogenous and orthotropic and is characterised via the following constitutive relationship (generalised Hooke’s law)[11]:

$$\sigma = C.\varepsilon \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon = S.\sigma \quad (2)$$

where σ : macrostress vector

ε : macrostrain vector

C: macroscale orthotropic elastic stiffness matrix

S: macroscale orthotropic elastic compliance matrix

This is a linear stress-strain relationship that is given by a six-by-six stiffness and compliance matrices C and S respectively. The assumption of material orthotropy considers the composite material to possess three mutually orthogonal planes of symmetry. The unit cell analysed in this work had the majority of reinforcing tows oriented in the longitudinal (one-two) plane and the transverse (two-one) plane. Also, the unit cell and binder path is symmetric and therefore balanced as such the angled binders are considered to cancel-out.

The objective is to determine the macroscale elastic stiffness matrix C, which is formulated by considering microscale response of the layers of reinforcement that make up the unit cell. By calculating the stiffness and compliance of every layer C^l and S^l then the overall macroscopic stiffness C can be determined based on the mathematical derivation that can be found in[6].

3 Methodology

The mathematical derivation[6] was incorporated into a computer model that was written in FORTRAN 95 to calculate the effective elastic stiffness of 3D woven angle interlock bound composite unit cells in the X, Y and Z axis. The model accepted geometric properties of the unit cell model calculated previously in Buchanan[5] and the material property data supplied by the respective manufacturers of the constituent parts of the composite. The principal differences in this model compared to the previous model developed by Wu et al [6] is the representation of the binder tow path and tow cross-sectional characteristics. In the previous model the tow path passed straight down T-T-T of the unit cell perpendicular to the warp and weft directions. However, in the present model the binder path does not pass directly T-T-T due to the nature of angle interlock bound weave architectures (figure 2). The previous model also assumed rectangular shaped tow cross-sections, but the present model takes into consideration here and in [5], cross-sections that deviate from rectangular e.g. elliptical or lentil shaped.

The 3D woven reinforcement was constructed using Toho Tenax HTS 12 k 820 g/1000 m for the stuffers and fillers with 6 k 400 g/1000 m binders on a modified Jacquard controlled weaving loom. The 3D woven angle interlock composite modelled here was manufactured into flat composite plaques using Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Moulding (VARTM). Subsequently the plaques were cut into tensile test samples along the longitudinal X axis direction and transverse Y axis direction so that E_x and E_y of the composite could be determined.

4 Results

The results recorded in table 1 indicates the geometric input parameters for the model where A_i and h_i are the cross sectional area and thickness of the stuffer, filler and binder (s , f , b) tows. The undulation factor (UF) was determined from optical microscopy of the consolidated composite plaques. The UF is measured for the nominally straight stuffer and filler tows and is the ratio of the straight length to the undulated length of the tow where a value of 1 is indicative of a completely straight tow. Measurement results of tow undulation on the 3D composite samples analysed here indicate that the stuffer and filler tows are nominally straight.

The experimental testing results were used to validate the present model with the new expressions exchanged for the equivalent terms used in the previous model[5] (table 2). It is not possible to directly compare modelled results in [5] as it was specifically formulated to evaluate orthogonal through thickness bound 3D weave unit cells. The results indicate that for the longitudinal modulus E_x both models predict to within 10% of the experimentally measured value. The previous model predicts the transverse modulus E_y over 18% compared to the experimental value in comparison to the present model predicting within 1% of the experimental value. The present model predicts in-plane shear modulus to 30% of the experimental value with the previous model 45% out.

5 Conclusions

The present model used new expressions to more accurately account for the volume fractions of individual elements and the contribution of a group of elements to a layer are more representative compared to the equivalent expressions used in the

previous approach described in [6]. Therefore, an advantage of the present model are the expressions that account for the cross sectional characteristics deviating from the previous assumption of rectangular tows. The assumption of rectangular cross section will lead to an overestimation in the fibre volume fraction resulting in inaccurate calculation of micromechanical stiffness constants. Where the arrangement of the reinforcement elements are more efficiently stacked i.e. in the case of ‘racetrack’ shaped tow cross sections then the previous approach may give more acceptable predictions. For the specific case examined in this paper the cross sectional characteristics of the stuffer tows (that contribute most to the longitudinal stiffness) are approximately rectangular shaped (figure 3) as such the previous model can calculate accurately the longitudinal modulus. However, the same is not true of the cross sections of the filler tows that contribute predominantly to the transverse modulus. Therefore, if for example a layer in the unit cell consists of oriented fibrous reinforcement elements and matrix elements the ‘weightings’ or contribution of the constituent elements to the layer are highly reliant on the ability to calculate the volume fraction of each element group accurately

Knock-down factors like those used in Cox[9] are not implemented in order to reduce the stiffness as a result of tow undulation. As such manufacture of the 3D woven composite is not required in the first instance. The nominally straight stuffer and filler tows present in the 3D woven composites manufactured in this work are as a consequence of strict control over the 3D weaving process. Therefore, the requirement to measure or empirically model what are statistical random features of the composite unit cell is reduced.

The prediction of in-plane shear modulus will need further investigation especially with regards to how to obtain a more representative experimental value of shear modulus. The experimental value indicated here was measured using V-notch beam Iosipescu shear test. The area of strain measurement is approximately 12mm^2 compared to the area of the unit cell of the 3D woven composite samples analysed in this work (1500mm^2). As a consequence only a small localised shear response is measured rather than the global material response.

The geometric model in Buchanan[5] and present model described here goes some way to address the needs of engineers and designers out in industry that generally wouldn’t appreciate the consequence of altering material and weaving parameters on the woven reinforcement on its subsequent mechanical properties. The present model can facilitate different reinforcement and matrix materials and by adjustment of the inputted weaving parameters can potentially make investigation easier.

Figure 1: model design system

Figure 2: Micrograph illustrating binder tow path

Figure 3: Micrograph along the transverse direction

Table 1: Geometric parameters

A_s (mm^2)	h_s (mm)	UF	A_f (mm^2)	h_f (mm)	UF	A_b (mm^2)	h_b (mm)
1.01	0.37	$0.9972 \pm 1.84 \times 10^{-4}$	0.55	0.26	$0.9967 \pm 2.45 \times 10^{-4}$	0.25	0.30

Table 2: Modelled and experimental results for 3D woven carbon fibre angle interlock composite

	E_x (GPa)	E_y (GPa)	E_z (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)
Previous Model (Wu)	67.37	70.70	8.72	2.27
Present Model	67.85	59.68	3.22	2.83
Experimental	61.7±1.60	59.70±2.10	-	4.12±0.06

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